

SOME COMMENTS ON THE PSYCHOLINGUISTIC FEATURES OF TEACHING READING AT NON-PHILOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY

Moydinova Shohida Ismailjanovna

Teacher of Andizhan State Institute of Foreign Languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10639361>

Annotation: This article describes the role of reading in teaching a foreign language, its psycholinguistic features. In particular, the features of teaching reading in English in non-philological universities, types of reading and its relationship with other speech activities were discussed.

Key words: *reading, combinations of letters, special texts, linguistic features of texts, cognitive process, complex process.*

Reading is understood as the process of perception of speech information, expressed in alphabetic characters, and the observation of its content.[1] Reading means finding the correct sound combinations of letters, combinations of letters, letters in words, correct reading and pronunciation without errors, finding the logical part and part of the sentence, reading it with the correct stress, rhythm and tone.[3] The linguistic component of reading is letter, words, phrases, sentences. Understanding the relationship between a letter and the sound it represents, that is, the relationship between sound and letter, is the first step in teaching reading techniques.

However, the minimum unit of learning to read is the word, and it allows you to master the technique of reading: in accordance with the rules of reading, connecting the graphic image of the word aloud or memorizing the image of the word, connecting this image with meaning.

Reading phrases teaches not only the pronunciation of the word, but also the placement of stresses according to the norms of the language. The same thing happens when reading sentences. The word, the smallest graphic unit that conveys meaning when reading, is conventionally taken as a unit of perception. The student needs to master a certain vocabulary. Words learned while reading are part of the passive vocabulary.

There are two types of passive vocabulary: real passive and potential passive. Passive vocabulary is the words that learners can learn from reading through their language experience. Potential vocabulary consists of words that were not previously used in speech, but whose meaning is revealed when reading without the help of information sources.[2]

When teaching text reading, a foreign language teacher should distinguish between texts taken from fiction and special texts, that is, texts related to a particular field, since teaching such texts requires a special approach.

The choice of teaching methods and techniques, taking into account the linguistic features of texts related to a special area, is important for the formation of reading skills specific to them, since the techniques used in each lesson differ depending on the purpose of the lesson.

Teaching students of non-philological faculties to understand the meaning of professional vocabulary, to distinguish between grammatical constructions characteristic of a professional text, while teaching students of non-philological faculties to read English texts, contributes to the formation of skills and competencies for the practical application of information obtained from professional vocabulary and corresponding to it.

Students may encounter various difficulties in reading professional texts that prevent them from understanding their content. Such difficulties include language difficulties associated

with vocabulary, grammatical structures and word order. For this reason, a foreign language teacher can identify such language difficulties in advance and plan the lesson in such a way as to increase the effectiveness of the lesson.

Among the difficulties in learning to read and understand professional texts related to a special field, the most common are lexical difficulties caused by a lack of students' vocabulary and ignorance of professional terms. The most important thing in understanding professional terms is that these terms have almost the same meaning when used in this area, and this should be taken into account by a teacher of a foreign language.

It should be noted that words consisting of two or more stems also cause difficulties. When studying lexical terms, it is advisable to start with the study of lexical terms consisting of international words.

Reading is considered a receptive speech activity, which consists of the perception and understanding of written speech. To understand the text being read, it is necessary to compare the written images of words with their sound-motor (motor) images, and the sound-motor images with their corresponding sounds.

Like other types of speech activity, reading is characterized by the mechanism of anticipation, the ability to correctly understand individual words, understand the word depending on the context, anticipate the words, sentences, understand. All researchers involved in the psychological problems of reading emphasize the need for the formation and development of anticipation.

The formation of reading technique is a long process, which is divided into different stages. These steps range from saying a sound to reading a text aloud. Each of these stages has its own characteristics and ways of acquiring them.

For example, A. N. Sokolov says that understanding a sentence goes through three stages: the first stage is the formation of a superficial idea in the student about the content of the entire sentence. This is called the first synthesis. The second stage of understanding is the analytical stage, which includes full pronunciation in inner and outer speech. The last, third stage is the stage of complete understanding of the sentence.

According to some authors, understanding the content of a text includes more than two stages. The main ones are:

- 1) the stage of understanding individual words, sentences and parts of the text, that is, the stage of partial understanding of the text;
- 2) the stage of understanding the text and its combinations, the meanings of sentences, that is, the stage of meanings;
- 3) the stage of understanding the content of the text, that is, the content stage.

The highest level of understanding is understanding at the level of content, which involves understanding what the main idea of the text is. The student must not only know the content of the text, but also know what the author wants to say through the actions of the characters in the work.

The cognitive process has a certain structure, in which the previous stage is included in the next one as an organizer. The psychological features of reading make it possible to determine the mechanisms or operations of reading in its formation as a speech activity. This includes mastering the written system of the language, developing a clear connection (association) between the letter and sound, knowing the rules for reading words, matching it with the

meaning and grammatical form, the processes of connecting words with phrases, sentences and texts.

In addition, in order to understand the text and its content, the reader must know a number of operations of text analysis and synthesis. It reflects such works as comparing individual parts of the text, linking the topic, basic facts with the idea, summing up, evaluating the content, understanding the thought based on the text and interpreting the text.

An analysis of reading as a type of speech activity shows that the process of reading and learning it is a complex process.

References:

1. Berman I.M., Bukhbinder V.A. Essays on the methodology of teaching reading in foreign languages, Kiyev, 1977, p-11.
2. Jalolov J. Methodology of foreign language teaching, Tashkent, "Teacher Publishing House", 1996, p-221.
3. Hoshimov U., Yaqubov I. English language teaching methodology. Tashkent, "Sharq" publishing house, 2003, p. 164.
4. Moydinova, S. I., & Gulomova, S. (2023). USING DIFFERENT TYPES OF EXERCISES IN TEACHING READING AT A NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 2(3), 69-72.
5. Moydinova, S. I., & Abdurahmanova, I. (2023). METHODS OF WORKING WITH LEXICAL MATERIAL AT THE INITIAL STAGE OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 2(3), 73-76.
6. Moydinova, S. I., & Khakimova, K. (2023). USING INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION FOR PRE-SCHOOL LEARNERS. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 2(3), 61-64.
7. Moydinova, S. I., & Bazarova, G. (2023). USING SONGS IN TEACHING ENGLISH FOR PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 2(3), 65-68.
8. Moydinova, S. I., & Abdumuminova, S. (2023). TYPES OF TEXTS BY SPECIALTY AND THEIR USAGE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES. "TRENDS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND PRACTICE", 1(1), 72-75.
9. Moydinova, S. (2022). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF NON-COMMUNICATIVE AND COMMUNICATIVE METHODS. Thematics Journal of Education, 7(1)..